

AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
CAKESHOP MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT
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ABSTRACT

A cake shop management system is a computerized management system. This system provides the Records of hardware assets beside software of the organization. the proposed system keep a track of different types of cakes available in the system.

The main objective of cake shop management system is to provide solution for the customers to manage their work using computerized process. this software application will help to handle the customer information details about the products, payment detailed information etc. detailed explanation about modules and design are provided in the documentation.

CHAPTER-1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction of the cake shop management system

The cake shop management system objectives is to provide a system which manages the sales activity in a cake shop for each day and its calculation which is very huge. The users will consume less amount of time when compared to manual paper work though the automated system.

The system will take care of all the sales servicing activity in a quick manner. Data storing is easier. It will be able to check any report at any time. Paper work and manual work is reduced. The system is user friendly and easy to use.

The cake shop management system activity is based on ordering the cakes for each customer. each customer will be given order number as soon as this the customer's name and contact details are added for reference. Next the cake is selected and stuffing type is also added if required. The user should enter the date of delivery and also the quantity. A separate bill is produced for the conformation and customer can do any advance payment during the day of delivery, the customer will be producing the bill of order. According to it, again a bill is generated of selling purpose and the customer should supposed to pay the balance amount. All the data's are being stored in the database.

- The customer can select the cake and order any number of quantities.
- The system will maintain the record of customers.
- The system will maintain the record of products.
- The system is very easy to access and user friendly.
- The customer can pay amount by credit card (or) cash on delivery.
- The system is maintaining particular way of ordering and also selling the product.

1.2. Existing System

Existing system study reveals that all the booking was done manually on registers, which was very tedious and error prone job. Searching and report generation was also possible in the existing system. Also the work of cake shop management was manually maintained. There was register (or) file system in the cake shop management, Present mode of working is based on manual system in which all the information is first received and entered in the register. It is very difficult job and time consuming also. Whenever we implement new system it is developed to remove the shortcoming of existing system .The computerized has more edge over the manual system. As we introduce the existing system, the existing system is based on the manual system, which takes lot of time to get performance of the test.

1.3. Proposed System

A new system will automate the whole working of cake shop. In this project we will retrieve the information of customer (or) update the information easily by the use of computer. In our proposed system we have the provision adding details of the cake shop. Another advantage of the system is that it is very easy to edit the details of the cake shop and delete the details of the cake shop when it is found unnecessary. Here no facility of net connection, e-mail facility is also not provided. Online order is not possible in this system. If new customer will come to buy any of the product it is stored the database. We can easily change, retrieve, save (or) delete the data in the database.

1.3.1. Aim of Project

The main of the cake shop management system is to provide solutions for the cake shop to manage their work using computerized process. this software application will help the admin to handle the customer information, details about the products, payment details, billing information etc.

1.3.2. Scope of the Project

- Reduction of the paper work
- Human initiative (or) manual labour may be significantly minimized.
- Large operations that are conducted manually can been completed in a matter of seconds.

CHAPTER-2

REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION

Hardware Requirement Specification:

- Processor : AMD A4, AMD Pro
- RAM : 4 GB
- Hard disk : 1 TB
- Key Board : Standard windows keyboard
- Mouse : Optical mouse

Software Requirement Specification:

- Operating System : Windows 7 Ultimate
- Programming Language : JAVA Swings
- IDE : Net beans 16
- Database : My SQL 8.0.32

CHAPTER-3

Software Development Process Model Adopted

This document plays a vital role in development of life cycle as it describes the complete requirements of the system. **SPIRAL MODEL** was defined by Barry Boehm in his 1998 article “A spiral models of Software Development and Enhancement”. This model was not the first model to discuss iterative development, but it was the first model to explain why the iteration models. Spiral model is a combination of sequential and prototype model. This model is best used for large projects which involves continuous enhancements. Where the output is a small prototype of the large software.

Iterative and Enhancement Model

Stages in SDLC

1. Feasibility analysis
2. Requirement analysis
3. Design
4. Coding
5. Testing
6. Maintenance

Feasibility analysis

Feasibility analysis includes analysis of project requirements in terms of input data and desired output, processing required to transform input into output, cost-benefit analysis, and schedule of the project.

Requirement analysis

Requirement analysis and specification includes gathering, analyzing, validating, and specifying requirements. At the end of this phase, the software Requirements Specification (SRS) document is prepared.

SRS is a formal document that acts as a written agreement between the development team and the customer. SRS acts as input to the design phase and includes functional, performance, software, hardware, and network requirements of the project.

Design

Design stage takes as its initial input the requirements identified in the approved requirements document. For each requirement, a set of one or more design elements will be produced as a result of interviews, workshops, and or prototype efforts. Design elements describe the desired software features in details, and generally include functional hierarchy diagrams, screen layout diagrams, tables of business rules, business process diagrams, pseudo code, and a complete entity-relationship diagram with a full data dictionary. Design phase includes translation of the requirements specified in the SRS into a logical structure that can be implemented in a programming language. The output of the design phase is a design document that acts as an input.

Coding

The coding stage takes as its primary input the design elements described in the approved design document. For each design element, a set of one or more software artefacts will be produced. Software artefacts include but are not limited to menus, dialogs, data management forms, data reporting formats, specialized procedures and functions. Appropriate test cases will be developed to guide users in their interactions with the software. Coding stage includes implementation of the design specified in the design document into executable programming language code.

Testing

Testing phase includes the detection of errors in the software. The testing process starts with a test plan that recognizes test-related activities, such as test case generation, testing criteria, and resource allocation for testing. The code is tested and mapped against the design document created in the design phase. The output of the testing phase is a test report containing errors that occurred while testing the application. During the integration and test stage, the software artefacts, online help, and test data are migrated from the development environment to a separate test environment.

Maintenance

Maintenance phase includes implementation of changes that software might undergo over a period of time, or implementation of new requirements after the software is deployed at the customer location. The maintenance phase also includes handling the residual errors that may exist in the software even after the testing phase. Maintenance team will start with requirement study, understanding of document later employee will be assigned work and they will undergo training on that particular assigned category.

System design

The developed application is considered to the version upon the system, which is proposed to be built with the content and touch of the My SQL as the centralized database. Java is the Front-end of the application. The entire application is designed in eclipse.

The initial phase of the proposed application development incorporates the basic software design models of the software engineering such as waterfall model, spiral model and conceptual model. The very beginning of the software application involves designing of the basic prototype model with the fundamental requirement specifications formed during the preparation of problem statement and the objectives to reach the customer or end-user requirement. Initially the system is designed with the following four modules

1-Registration module

2-Transaction module

3-Login module

All the above said modules are the core functionalities of the proposed ATM system simulation. The application is developed in such a way, where any forms or module can be changed or updated with a new requirement of the client. This flexibility is achieved through the spiral software model, because the spiral approach is a combination of sequential and prototype. This features in spiral model will make the software developers to include during the new software application development, especially in developing large projects which includes a major enhancements and frequent changes or updating to reach the client functional requirements.

CHAPTER-4
DESIGN MODELS

Class Diagram:

Use Case Diagram:

Sequence Diagram:

Activity Diagram:

CHAPTER-5

Implementation

Implementation is the stage of the project when the theoretical design is turned into working system. It can be considered to be the most critical stage in achieving a successful new system and in giving the user, confidence that the new system will work and effective. The goal of the coding phase is to translate the design into code in the given programming language. The coding steps translate the detailed design of the system into programming language. The translation process continues when the compiler accepts source code as input and produces machine dependent object code as output. Linking of object files are done to produce the machine code. Internal documentation is another important factor, to facilitate others to understand the code and the logic.

My SQL

My SQL is an open-source relational database management system (RDBMS). Its name is a combination of "My", the name of co-founder Michael Widenius's daughter and "SQL" is the abbreviation for Structured Query Language. My SQL is free and open-source software under the terms of the GNU General Public License, and is also available under a variety of proprietary licenses. My SQL was owned and sponsored by the Swedish company My SQL AB, which was bought by Sun Microsystems.

My SQL is a component of the LAMP web application software stack (and others), which is an acronym for Linux, Apache, My SQL, Perl/PHP/Python. My SQL is used by many database-driven web applications, including Drupal, Joomla, phpBB, and Word Press. My SQL is also used by many popular websites, including Facebook, Flickr, Media Wiki, Twitter, and YouTube.

We want the My SQL database to be:

- Easy to use
- Free from Bugs
- Available and affordable for all
- Fun to operate and improve

Eclipse

Eclipse is an integrated development environment (IDE) used in computer programming, and is the most widely used Java IDE. It contains a base workspace and an extensible plug-in system for customizing the environment. Eclipse is written mostly in Java and its primary use is for developing Java applications, but it may also be used to develop applications in other programming languages through the use of plugins, including: Adda, ABAP, C, C++, COBOL, D, Fortran, Haskell, JavaScript, Julia, Lasso, Lua, NATURAL, Perl, PHP, Prolog, Python, R, Ruby (including Ruby on Rails framework), Rust, Scala, Clojure, Groovy, Scheme, and Erlang. It can also be used to develop documents with Latex (through the use of the TeXlipse plugin) and packages for the software Mathematica. Development environments include the Eclipse Java development tools (JDT) for Java and Scala, Eclipse CDT for C/C++ and Eclipse PDT for PHP, among others.

The initial codebase originated from IBM Visual Age. The Eclipse software development kit (SDK), which includes the Java development tools, is meant for Java developers. Users can extend its abilities by installing plug-ins written for the Eclipse Platform, such as development toolkits for other programming languages, and can write and contribute their own plug-in modules.

Released under the terms of the Eclipse Public License, Eclipse SDK is free and open-source software, although it is incompatible with the GNU General Public License. It was one of the first IDEs to run under GNU Class path and it runs without problems under Iced Tea.

Programming Language

Java

Java is a general-purpose programming language that is class-based, object-oriented, and designed to have as few implementation dependencies as possible. It is intended to let application developers write once, run anywhere (WORA), meaning that compiled Java code can run on all platforms that support Java without the need for recompilation. Java applications are typically compiled to byte code that can run on any Java virtual machine (JVM) regardless of the underlying computer architecture.

- Java is a programmer's language
- Java is cohesive and consistent
- Except for those constraint imposed by the Internet environment. Java gives the programmer complete control

Sun Microsystems released the first public implementation as Java 1.0 in 1996. It provides no-cost run-times on popular platforms. Fairly secure and featuring configurable security, it allowed network- and file-access restrictions. Major web browsers soon incorporated the ability to run Java applets within web pages, and Java quickly became popular. Other possible advantages of Java include

- Object-oriented
- Platform independence
- Excellent networking capabilities
- Wide variety of Application Programmer Interfaces (APIs)

Java is platform independent

Java technology is said to be platform independent due to its flexible supporting on all available operating systems with respect to its development and compilation. (Platform represents Operating System). Java is a platform independent programming language, because when you install Java Development Toolkit software on your system then automatically Java Virtual Machine are installed on your system. For every operating system separate JVM is available which is capable to read the **.class** file or **byte code**.

Figure 1: Java is Platform Independent

Java Swing

Swing is a GUI widget toolkit for Java. Swing was developed to provide a more sophisticated set of GUI components than the earlier Abstract Window Toolkit (AWT). Swing provides a look and feel that emulates the look and feel of several platforms, and also allows applications to have a look and feel unrelated to the underlying platform. It has more powerful and flexible components than AWT. In addition to familiar components such as buttons, check boxes and labels, Swing provides several advanced components such as tabbed panel, scroll panes, trees, tables, and lists. Unlike AWT components, Swing components are not implemented by platform-specific code. Instead, they are written entirely in Java and therefore are platform-independent. The term "lightweight" is used to describe such an element.

Figure 2: Swing Hierarchy

Swing Packages

Some of the packages in Swing

1. javax.swing.text
2. javax.swing.plaf.multi
3. javax.swing.text.html
4. javax.swing.text.html.parser
5. javax.swing.text.rtf
6. javax.swing.tree
7. javax.swing.undo
8. javax.accessibility
9. javax.swing
10. javax.swing.border

Advantages of Swing

1. Provides both additional functionalities and added components to AWT-replacement components
2. Swing components are platform-independent.
3. Swing components can use a different look and feel.
4. Swing components use the Model-View-Controller paradigm (MVC) and thus can provide a much more flexible UI.
5. Swing components are lightweight (are less resource-intensive than AWT).
6. Swing provides built-in double buffering.
7. Swing provides paint debugging support for when you build your own components.

CHAPTER-6**SAMPLE CODING****Login Page**

```
import java.awt.*;
import javax.swing.*;
import java.awt.event.*;
import java.sql.*;

public class first_atm extends JFrame implements ActionListener{
    JTextField txtuser=new JTextField(25);
    JPasswordField txtpass=new JPasswordField(25);
    JLabel lbluser=new JLabel("Username: ");
    JLabel lblpass=new JLabel("Pin Number: ");
    JButton btnOk=new JButton(new ImageIcon("register.jpg"));
    JButton btnRegister=new JButton(new ImageIcon("button.jpg"));
    //JButton btnBlock = new JButton("Lock Account >>");
    Connection cn;
    Statement st;
    PreparedStatement ps;
    public first_atm(){
        JPanel pane=new JPanel();
        pane.setLayout(null);
        pane.add(txtuser);
        pane.add(txtpass);
        pane.add(lbluser);
        pane.add(lblpass);
        pane.add(btnOk);
        pane.add(btnRegister);
        lbluser.setBounds(10,20,80,20);
        lblpass.setBounds(10,40,80,20);
        txtuser.setBounds(100,20,100,20);
        txtpass.setBounds(100,40,100,20);
        btnOk.setBounds(50,70,75,20);
```

```

btnRegister.setBounds(125,70,83,20);
btnOk.addActionListener(this);
btnRegister.addActionListener(this);
setContentPane(pane);
setDefaultCloseOperation(JFrame.EXIT_ON_CLOSE);
JLabel lbl = new JLabel();
lbl.setBounds(0,0,250,150);
pane.add(lbl);
try{
Class.forName("com.mysql.jdbc.Driver");
cn = DriverManager.getConnection("jdbc:mysql://localhost:3306/atm","root","root");
}catch(ClassNotFoundException e) {
System.err.println("Failed to load driver");
e.printStackTrace();
}catch(SQLException e){
System.err.println("Unable to connect");
e.printStackTrace();
}
}
public void actionPerformed(ActionEvent e){
Object source=e.getSource()
if(source==btnOk){
try{
String str1=txtuser.getText();
String str2=txtpass.getText();
if((str1.length()==0 || str2.length()==0)){
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Cannot be
Process","WARNING",JOptionPane.WARNING_MESSAGE);
}
else{
st=cn.createStatement();
String strUser="";
String strPass="";
ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery("SELECT * FROM tbl_list WHERE UserName='"+str1+"'");
while(rs.next()){

```

```

strUser=rs.getString(1);
strPass=rs.getString(4);
}
st.close();
if(strUser.equals(str1)){
if(strPass.equals(str2)){
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Welcome
"+txtuser.getText(),"Welcome",JOptionPane.INFORMATION_MESSAGE);
third_atm panel = new third_atm();
panel.setSize(330,300);
panel.setVisible(true);
panel.setResizable(false);
panel.setLocation(400,250);
dispose();
}else{
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Username found but the password is incorrect!","Security
Pass",JOptionPane.WARNING_MESSAGE);
txtpass.requestFocus(true);
}
}else{
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Username is incorrect!","Security
Pass",JOptionPane.WARNING_MESSAGE);
txtuser.requestFocus(true);
}
}
}catch(SQLException w){
}
}else if(source==btnRegister){
second_atm panel = new second_atm();
panel.setSize(370,400);
panel.setVisible(true);
panel.setResizable(false);
panel.setLocation(400,250);
dispose();
}
}

```

```

else if(source == btnBlock){
int n=JOptionPane.showConfirmDialog(null,"If you lock this account,you cannot access this
Any more.Are you sure you want to Lock this
account?","Warning",JOptionPane.YES_NO_OPTION);
if(n==JOptionPane.YES_OPTION){
try{
st=cn.createStatement();
String strUser="";
String strPass="";
ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery("SELECT * FROM

WHERE UserName='"+txtuser.getText()+"");
while(rs.next()){
strUser=rs.getString(1);
strPass=rs.getString(5);
}
if(strUser.equals(txtuser.getText())){
if(strPass.equals(txtpass.getText())){
ps = cn.prepareStatement("DELETE FROM tbl_Info WHERE UserName = '"+ txtuser.getText() +
"");
ps.executeUpdate();
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Your Account has been successfully
Lock.", "ATM",JOptionPane.INFORMATION_MESSAGE);
txtuser.requestFocus(true);
txtuser.setText("");
txtpass.setText("");
}else{
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Username found but the Pin Number is
incorrect!","Security Pass",JOptionPane.WARNING_MESSAGE);
txtpass.requestFocus(true);
}
}else{
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Username is incorrect!","Security
Pass",JOptionPane.WARNING_MESSAGE);
txtuser.requestFocus(true);
}
}

```

```
}  
}  
catch(SQLException s){  
System.out.print("SQL statement is not executed!");  
}  
catch(Exception j){  
j.printStackTrace();  
}  
}  
}*/  
}  
public static void main(String[]args){  
first_atm log=new first_atm();  
log.setLocation(400,250);  
log.setSize(250,150);  
log.setTitle("Log-In");  
log.setResizable(false);  
log.setVisible(true);  
}  
}
```

Register Page

```
import javax.swing.*;
import java.awt.*;
import java.awt.event.*;
import java.sql.*;

public class second_atm extends JFrame implements ActionListener
{
public static void main(String[]args){
second_atm panel = new second_atm();
panel.setSize(450,450);
panel.setVisible(true);
panel.setResizable(false);
panel.setLocation(400,250);
}
Font fl = new Font("", Font.BOLD, 10);
JLabel lblUser = new JLabel("User Name ",JLabel.RIGHT);
JLabel lblFName = new JLabel("First Name ",JLabel.RIGHT);
JLabel lblVPass = new JLabel("Verify Pin Number ",JLabel.RIGHT);
JLabel lblLName = new JLabel("Last Name ",JLabel.RIGHT);
JTextField txtFName= new JTextField(20);
JTextField txtLName = new JTextField(20);
JPasswordField txtPass= new JPasswordField(20);
JPasswordField txtVPass = new JPasswordField(20);
JTextField txtday = new JTextField(20);
JTextField txtmonth = new JTextField(20);
JTextField txtyear = new JTextField(20);
JTextField txtCash = new JTextField(20);
JTextField txtPhone = new JTextField(20);
JButton btnCret = new JButton(new ImageIcon("reg.jpg"));
Connection cn;
Statement st;
PreparedStatement ps;
```

```

public void clear()
{
txtUser.setText("");
txtFName.setText("");
txtPass.setText("");
txtLName.setText("");
txtVPass.setText("");
}
lbl.setBounds(0,0,500,500);
pane.add(lbl);
setContentPane(pane);
setDefaultCloseOperation(JFrame.EXIT_ON_CLOSE);
pane.setBorder(BorderFactory.createTitledBorder(
BorderFactory.createEtchedBorder(), "Registration Form"));
try{
Class.forName("com.mysql.jdbc.Driver");
cn = DriverManager.getConnection("jdbc:mysql://localhost:3306/atm","root","root");
}catch(ClassNotFoundException e) {
System.err.println("Failed to load driver");
e.printStackTrace();
}
catch(SQLException e){
System.err.println("Unable to connect");
e.printStackTrace();
}
}

public void actionPerformed(ActionEvent e){
Object source = e.getSource();
if(source == btnCret){
String suser = txtUser.getText();
String sname = txtFName.getText();
String spass = txtPass.getText();
String slname = txtLName.getText();
String svpass = txtVPass.getText();
String sphono = txtPhone.getText();

```

```

if((suser.length()==0 || sname.length()==0 || spass.length()==0 || slname.length()==0 ||
svpass.length()==0 )){
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Some Fields are
empty", "WARNING",JOptionPane.WARNING_MESSAGE);
}
else if(spass.length()>4)
{
txtPass.setText("");
txtVPass.setText("");
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Invalid
password", "WARNING",JOptionPane.WARNING_MESSAGE);
}
else if(sphono.length()>10 || sphono.length()<10)
{
txtPhone.setText("");
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Enter a vaild Phone
number", "WARNING",JOptionPane.WARNING_MESSAGE);
}
else{
if(spass.equals(svpass)){
boolean xx = false;
try{
st= cn.createStatement();
rs=st.executeQuery("SELECT * FROM tbl_list WHERE Password = " + spass + "");
while(rs.next()){
String spass2 =rs.getString(4);
xx = true;
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Pincode already
used", "Information",JOptionPane.INFORMATION_MESSAGE);
}
st.close();
if(xx==false){
try{
st= cn.createStatement();
catch(SQLException s){

```

```
System.out.println("SQL Error" + s.toString() + " " + s.getErrorCode() + " " + s.getSQLState());
}
catch(Exception x){
System.out.println("Error" + x.toString()+" " + x.getMessage());
}
}
else{
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Verify your
password.", "ATM" ,JOptionPane.INFORMATION_MESSAGE);
}
```

Withdraw Page

```
import java.awt.*;
import javax.swing.*;
import java.awt.event.*;
import java.sql.*;

public class wdraw_trans extends JFrame implements ActionListener{
    JPasswordField txtuser=new JPasswordField(25);
    JTextField txtpass=new JTextField(25);
    JTextField txtwid=new JTextField(25);
    JLabel lbluser=new JLabel("Pin Number: ");
    JLabel lblpass=new JLabel("WithDraw: ");
    JLabel lblwid=new JLabel("Balanced: ");
    pane.add(txtwid);
    pane.add(lbluser);
    pane.add(lblpass);
    pane.add(lblwid);
    pane.add(btnOk);
    pane.add(btnRegister);
    BorderLayout.createEtchedBorder(), "Withdraw Transaction"));
    JLabel lbl = new JLabel(new ImageIcon(""));
    lbl.setBounds(0,0,250,200);
    pane.add(lbl);
    }else{
    if(b<10){
    int sum = a-b;
    txtpass.setText((sum+""));
    txtwid.setText("");
    ps.executeUpdate();
    txtuser.requestFocus(true);
    }
    }
    }st.close();
    }catch(NumberFormatException nfe){
```

```

JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Enter now the amount to
withdraw","ATM",JOptionPane.INFORMATION_MESSAGE);
}
}
public static void main(String[]args){
wdraw_trans log=new wdraw_trans();
log.setLocation(400,250);
log.setSize(250,200);
log.setResizable(false);
log.setVisible(true);
}
}

```

Balance Page

```

import java.awt.*;
import javax.swing.*;
import java.awt.event.*;
import java.sql.*;

public class bal_trans extends JFrame implements ActionListener{

JPasswordField txtuser=new JPasswordField(25);
JTextField txtpass=new JTextField(25);
JLabel lbluser=new JLabel("Pin Number: ");
JLabel lblpass=new JLabel("Balanced");
JButton btnOk=new JButton("Back to Menu");
JButton btnRegister=new JButton("Bal.Inquire");
pane.add(txtuser);
pane.add(txtpass);
pane.add(lbluser);
pane.add(lblpass);
pane.add(btnOk);
pane.add(btnRegister);
txtpass.setBounds(100,40,100,20);
btnOk.setBounds(80,120,140,20);
btnRegister.setBounds(100,70,100,20);

```

```

btnOk.setForeground(Color.yellow);
btnRegister.setForeground(Color.yellow);
btnOk.setBackground(Color.black);
btnRegister.setBackground(Color.black);
setContentPane(pane);
setDefaultCloseOperation(JFrame.DO_NOTHING_ON_CLOSE);
} catch(SQLException e){
System.err.println("Unable to connect");
e.printStackTrace();
}
ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery("SELECT * FROM tbl_list WHERE Password
='"+txtuser.getText()+"'");
while(rs.next()){
txtpass.setText(rs.getString(9));
JOptionPane.showMessageDialog(null,"Record Found.", "ATM
System",JOptionPane.INFORMATION_MESSAGE);

}
st.close();
}
catch(SQLException s){
System.out.println("No record found!\n\n");
System.out.println("SQL Error" + s.toString() + " " + s.getErrorCode() + " " + s.getSQLState());
}
catch(Exception x){
System.out.println("Error" + x.toString()+" " + x.getMessage());
}

}
}

public static void main(String[]args){
bal_trans log=new bal_trans();
}

```

Testing

Testing is a process, which reveals errors in the program. It is the major quality measure employed during software development. During testing, the program is executed with a set of test cases and the output of the program for the test cases is evaluated to determine if the program is performing as it is expected to perform.

Testing Strategies**Unit Testing**

Unit testing focuses verification effort on smallest unit of software design module. All the modules in this system are tested under this strategy of unit test. In this each line of the code were tested. We encountered several general syntax errors, which we corrected during the compilation. In the Login Page we check for username and password if valid username and password is given then it proceeds to main page.

In registration module we enroll a new user with submitting primary credentials. In transaction module we deal with all the banking services provided by the application.

Integration Testing

Integration testing ensures that software and subsystems work together a whole. It tests the interface of all the modules to make sure that the modules behave properly when integrated together. The goal of this testing is to detect design errors, while focusing on testing the interconnection between modules.

In this testing we check whether the number of text fields specified in the design should match with the number of entities in the database.

Validation Testing

The process of evaluating software during the development process or at the end of the development process to determine whether it satisfies specified requirements. Validation Testing ensures that the product actually meets the client's needs. It can also be defined as to demonstrate that the product fulfils its intended use when deployed on appropriate environment.

System Testing

Here the entire software system is tested. The reference document for this process is the requirements document, and the goals to see if software meets its requirements. Here entire software has been tested against requirements of project and it is checked whether all requirements of project have been satisfied or not.

The screenshot shows a window titled "Project" with a light blue background. It contains a registration form with the following fields and labels:

- User Name
- First Name
- Last Name
- Pin Number
- Verify Pin Number
- B-Day: Day , Month , Year
- Phone number
- Cash Tender

At the bottom of the form is a green button with the text "REGISTER" and a right-pointing arrow.

Register Page

The screenshot shows a window titled "Log-In" with a light gray background. It contains a login form with the following fields and labels:

- Username:
- Pin Number:

At the bottom of the form are two buttons: a dark green button with "LOGIN" and a right-pointing arrow, and a light green button with "REGISTER" and a right-pointing arrow.

Login Page (Registered users only)

Main menu Page

Deposit

Withdraw Page

Transfer Page

Balance enquiry

Logout

CHAPTER-9

Conclusion

The ATM system simulator is designed and implemented to reach the functional requirements and objectives of the end user. The system is secured by providing the authenticated 4 digit PIN, which is the gateway to the application. The customer can function all the transactions in a secured manner and use the application at any time in any place. This system is designed to benefit all its customers to use in more effective & authenticated way. This simulator will provide the environment in which new enhancements can be performed on it.

Future enhancement

The following enhancements can be done for the project.

- Use of Bio-metric authentication (Finger Print) can improve more security.
- Mini statement field can be added for the application.
- Improved GUI can be updated.

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